

Fine-grained Open-vocabulary Object Detection

Lorenzo Bianchi ¹,
Fabrizio Falchi ¹

¹CNR-ISTI, Via G. Moruzzi, 1, 56124, Pisa, Italy.

²University of Pisa, Computer Engineering Department, Via Caruso, 15, 56122, Pisa, Italy.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): lorenzo.bianchi@isti.cnr.it;

Contributing authors: fabio.carrara@isti.cnr.it; nicola.messina@isti.cnr.it;

claudio.gennaro@isti.cnr.it; fabrizio.falchi@isti.cnr.it;

Abstract

The emergence of vision-language models like CLIP has significantly advanced open-vocabulary object detection, enabling object recognition through free-text descriptions at inference time. However, existing approaches primarily focus on class-level discrimination, often failing to capture fine-grained object attributes such as color, pattern, and material. In this paper, we introduce Fine-Grained Open-Vocabulary Object Detection and propose a benchmark suite to assess the ability of models to detect, differentiate, and describe objects with fine-grained attributes, even in the presence of challenging negative captions. Our benchmark suite covers multiple difficulty levels and attribute types, providing a comprehensive evaluation of state-of-the-art open-vocabulary object detectors. Extensive experiments reveal that most detection models struggle to capture subtle object attributes effectively. In order to mitigate the critical failures of the probed models, we prepare a weakly labeled training set and introduce a distillation-based adaptation method that balances attribute-level and class-level detection. This approach improves the trade-off between fine- and coarse-grained recognition, helping to bridge the gap that emerges in current state-of-the-art models. Our results highlight current limitations and suggest promising directions for improving fine-grained open-world detection. Data and code are available at <https://lorebianchi98.github.io/FG-OVD/>.

Keywords: Open-vocabulary detection, Fine-grained understanding, Benchmark, Dataset

1 Introduction

Do you remember the iconic scene in *Terminator* where the T-800 scans the parking lot outside the Bar Corral? His vision is augmented by detailed data on each vehicle — make, model, condition, and whether it is suitable for escape. Although entertaining in a cinematic context, this glimpse into a robot’s perspective highlights a central challenge of modern computer vision,

that is, understanding the fine-grained differences between objects.

Of course, this is an amusing example that captures well the essence of fine-grained object detection tasks: identifying subtle differences in object properties, such as color, texture, or material, even in the presence of similar distractors. Unlike coarse-grained detection, where recognizing broad categories (e.g., ‘car’ versus ‘motorcycle’) is sufficient, fine-grained detection requires models to go

deeper, discerning the complex details that could define an object.

Open-vocabulary object detection (OVD) is the task of localizing and classifying objects that were not encountered during training, overcoming the limitations of traditional detectors restricted to a fixed set of classes. Recent advances in visual language models, such as CLIP (Radford et al., 2021), have spurred advances in OVD by establishing semantic connections between image regions and text labels, even when the labels describe complex properties. This flexibility has opened up applications in fields such as autonomous driving (Ma et al., 2022), extended reality (Lu et al., 2023), and robotics (Liang et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2023; Jatavallabhula et al., 2023).

Given its need for flexible taxonomies, OVD allows object labels to go beyond simple categorical terms, thus enabling, in principle, the use of any natural language freeform text to populate the vocabulary. This paradigm shift allows incorporating fine-grained details such as color, pattern, and material into the labels, unveiling fine-grained recognition tasks requiring the distinction between, for example, a *brown bear* and a *polar bear* or a *dark brown wooden lamp* and a *gray metal lamp*. This task, which we call **Fine-Grained Open-Vocabulary Detection (FG-OVD)**, pushes the boundaries of object detection by requiring models to discern complex and subtle differences among the objects.

Currently, traditional open-vocabulary object detection (Lin et al., 2014; Gupta et al., 2019) benchmarks are limited to class-level labels, failing to assess models’ capabilities with more detailed textual descriptions. Despite some attempts to address fine-grained understanding in object detection (Ramanathan et al., 2023; Bravo et al., 2023), a comprehensive investigation of how effective open-ended vocabulary detectors are in discerning fine-grained properties of objects remains largely unexplored. This gap becomes critical in some emerging problems, such as episodic memory in egocentric videos, where the ability to retrieve object instances based on specific attributes is required.

To address this challenge, we present a suite of benchmarks tailored for FG-OVD tasks. This suite systematically assesses the ability of a model to detect, distinguish, and describe fine-grained

object attributes using eight annotated image sets, a dedicated evaluation protocol, and specific metrics. Each benchmark instance includes an image with object locations described by a detail-rich caption and negative examples that test the model’s ability to identify the correct attributes. This paper extends our previous CVPR Highlight paper (Bianchi et al., 2024), in which we employed such benchmarks to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of advanced OVD methods, providing insight into their limitations in capturing fine-grained details.

In this work, we further advance the research in FG-OVD by proposing a solution to mitigate the critically low performance obtained by current state-of-the-art models. Specifically, we provide a weakly labeled training set constructed by employing a similar pipeline to the one used to generate the test sets of the benchmarks and designed to fine-tune OVD models to make them more sensitive to fine-grained descriptions. Furthermore, employing the proposed FG-OVD training set, we introduce and deeply study **NoctOWL (Not only coarse-text Open-World Localizer)**, the first open-vocabulary detector designed for tackling FG-OVD by employing a simple yet clever adaptation strategy. NoctOWL is designed to capture subtle, fine-grained object attributes by adapting the classification head to be more discriminative to details while remaining resilient to coarse-grained concepts. This is obtained by adjusting the small linear classification layer on the introduced training set and incorporating a distillation loss that keeps the model able to understand coarse-grained concepts. With this model, we show that it is relatively simple to bridge the gap between fine- and coarse-grained detection performance, by also mitigating the risk of overfitting on the employed training split. Evaluating this model provides deeper insight into the trade-offs models face between fine-grained specificity and broad generalization.

In summary, the paper makes the following key contributions:

- We release a comprehensive benchmark suite to test models’ ability to recognize fine-grained objects’ properties — such as color, material, and pattern — and to analyze the limitations of state-of-the-art detectors.

- We leverage an LLM to generate a weakly labeled training set specifically designed for fine-grained open-vocabulary detection.
- We present NoctOWL, a distillation-based baseline model that enhances FG-OVD performance while improving the trade-off between fine- and coarse-grained detection.
- We evaluate pre-trained open-vocabulary detectors and our proposed model on our novel benchmark suite, showing the ability of NoctOWL to effectively tackle the FG-OVD task with respect to the probed state-of-the-art methods.

We provide code for reproducing the results and checkpoints of the trained models at <https://lorebianchi98.github.io/FG-OVD/>.

2 Related work

Open-vocabulary detection (OVD) aims to enhance detection capabilities beyond the limited set of labeled base classes used during training. Its goal is to identify novel classes, which may include free-form text, during inference.

An early effort in open-vocabulary object detection, such as Bansal et al. (2018), replaced the final classification layer with linguistic embeddings such as GloVe (Pennington et al., 2014) to represent class names. The advent of vision-linguistic models, including CLIP (Radford et al., 2021) and ALIGN (Jia et al., 2021), trained on large image-text datasets, dramatically improved the semantic alignment between visual and textual data.

These advances in cross-modal alignment have been included in several open vocabulary detectors, e.g., by introducing strategies for replacing the final class features with text embeddings (Zhou et al., 2022; Minderer et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2022; Kuo et al., 2023; Minderer et al., 2023), by further refining the ROI-Align head (He et al., 2017) by exploiting pre-trained vision-language backbones (Gu et al., 2022; Du et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2022; Kuo et al., 2023; Minderer et al., 2023), or by adapting CLIP directly for open vocabulary detection (Zhong et al., 2022; Minderer et al., 2022, 2023).

More recent studies (Li et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023; Kamath et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022) have investigated the integration of open-ended

vocabulary detection with tasks such as Referring Expression Comprehension (REC) (Yu et al., 2016; Mao et al., 2016) and Phrase Grounding (PG) (Mu et al., 2021; Plummer et al., 2015). Although both focus on a single possibly complex phrase, the former focuses on identifying a single object within the image. At the same time, the latter aims to identify all entities mentioned in the text. However, there are many noticeable differences between the above-mentioned tasks and FG-OVD. In fact, (i) models trained for these tasks are generally not evaluated for their ability to handle difficult distinctions, and (ii) REC and PG assume that the given sentence unambiguously refers to an object in the image, reducing the need for sophisticated discriminative skills.

Although some REC and PG models, such as GroundingDino (Liu et al., 2023) and GLIP (Zhang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2022), can be used as open vocabulary detectors, they often have limitations when they need to distinguish subtle fine-grained differences.

Concerning benchmarks for open-vocabulary detection, the COCO (Lin et al., 2014) and LVIS (Gupta et al., 2019) datasets are widely recognized for evaluating the localization and classification capabilities of object detectors. Initially used to evaluate closed-set detectors, the COCO dataset was later adapted for zero-shot (Bansal et al., 2018) and open-vocabulary (Gu et al., 2022; Zhong et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023) detection. In this context, COCO includes 48 basic categories for training and 17 new categories for testing.

In contrast, LVIS offers a more extensive and diverse set of object categories organized by frequency of appearance (common, frequent, and rare). Several studies (Gu et al., 2022; Zhong et al., 2022; Kuo et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023) have used the frequent and common categories as the basis, while the rare categories have been used for testing. Although these benchmarks are useful for evaluating open-vocabulary zero-shot detection, they do not specifically measure the model’s ability to identify specific attributes of objects.

OVAD (Bravo et al., 2023) and VAW (Pham et al., 2021) are the datasets closest to our objectives. Although they focus on object attributes and propose negative samples to challenge existing detectors, our proposed method differs consistently. In fact, (i) these already existing benchmarks mainly evaluate attribute detectors, which

Fig. 1: Fine-grained Open-Vocabulary Detection (FG-OVD). **A.** We generate fine-grained captions of objects based on their parts and corresponding attributes. We obtain object-specific vocabularies comprised of one positive caption — generated by an LLM based on a semi-structured description — and several negative captions built via attribute substitution. **B.** From the obtained weakly-supervised dataset, we manually curate a suite of benchmarks (**FG-OVD Benchmarks**) by manipulating negative sets according to their difficulty levels or the types of attributes altered — categorized as **Difficulty-based** and **Attribute-based** benchmarks — to probe the ability of state-of-the-art open-vocabulary detectors to discern detailed object properties. We also compile and release a weakly-labeled train and validation set (**FG-OVD Train Sets**). **C.** We use the provided resources to get insights into the capabilities of existing detectors and their limitations. **D.** We train, analyze, and release *NoctOWL*, a model with improved performance in fine-grained domains.

usually include a head dedicated to attribute inference in addition to object classes; (ii) they rely on structured annotations instead of natural language descriptions for each object, limiting the evaluation of state-of-the-art vision-language models; (iii) they do not include specially designed negative examples, limiting an in-depth analysis of the limitations of current detectors.

The PACO (Ramanathan et al., 2023) dataset was a source of inspiration for our work. It is built on the basis of COCO and includes bounding box annotations enriched with structured descriptions in JSON format containing information about attributes and parts of objects. PACO also incorporates external, categorized properties such as colors, materials, and patterns. Our benchmark suite builds on PACO by generating detailed natural language descriptions from these structured

annotations using large language models (LLMs). This approach aligns with the growing trend of leveraging LLMs to produce high-quality, diverse, targeted annotations (Momeni et al., 2023).

3 Methodology

We propose a dedicated benchmark suite to assess how well open-vocabulary object detectors identify fine-grained object characteristics. In subsection 3.1, we formally define the problem and introduce a structured evaluation framework. Next, in subsection 3.2, we introduce the dataset specifically designed to evaluate the ability of open-vocabulary detectors to distinguish fine-grained object attributes, along with a training set aimed at enhancing their performance. Finally, in subsection 3.3, we provide a comprehensive overview of

NoctOWL, our baseline model for FG-OVD, and its training procedure.

3.1 Evaluation Protocol

Consider an image $I \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times C}$ and a vocabulary $\mathcal{V} = \{c_j\}_{j=1}^T$, comprising T textual descriptions of target objects. An open-vocabulary object detector ψ processes I and \mathcal{V} to generate a set of m detections $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathbf{d}_i\}_{i=1}^m$, where each detection $\mathbf{d}_i = (\mathbf{b}_i, \mathbf{s}_i)$ consists of a bounding box $\mathbf{b}_i \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and confidence scores $\mathbf{s}_i \in \mathbb{R}^T$. Each entry $s_{i,j}$ in \mathbf{s}_i reflects the likelihood of the detected object corresponding to the vocabulary entry c_j ¹. For every detection, the vocabulary item with the highest confidence score is chosen as the predicted label.

In evaluation scenarios, such as zero-shot or open-vocabulary detection, the vocabulary \mathcal{V} is predefined and consistent across the test set. Detections \mathcal{D} are evaluated by comparing them with the m' ground truth annotations $\mathcal{O} = \{\mathbf{o}_i\}_{i=1}^{m'}$, where each ground truth object $\mathbf{o}_i = (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_i, y_i)$ includes the correct bounding box $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and its correct label $y_i \in \mathcal{V}$. Performance is measured using standard object detection metrics, such as mean Average Precision (mAP).

Dynamic Vocabularies for FG-OVD

To evaluate FG-OVD, we propose a refined approach that uses a customized dictionary \mathcal{V}_i for each ground truth object \mathbf{o}_i . Unlike conventional evaluation methods that rely on a fixed vocabulary shared across all objects, this approach introduces object-specific vocabularies, offering fine-grained control over the selection of both positive and negative samples for each object.

Specifically, each ground truth object \mathbf{o}_i is associated with a detailed textual description c_i^{pos} , referred to as the *positive caption*, which provides an accurate textual representation of the visual characteristics of the object. In addition to the positive caption, the object \mathbf{o}_i is linked to a set of *negative captions* $\{c_{i,1}^{\text{neg}}, c_{i,2}^{\text{neg}}, \dots, c_{i,N}^{\text{neg}}\}$. These negative captions describe concepts or objects that are semantically different from the positive caption for the given object. For instance, taking a positive caption like "a glass lamp emitting yellow

¹Vocabulary entries are often generated by expanding class labels into descriptive captions, e.g., the label *dog* might become a *photo of a dog*.

Fig. 2: Examples of Dynamic Vocabularies: The image I features three objects, each associated with a vocabulary. The positive captions c^{pos} (marked with \checkmark) — *A light grey stone bench* and *A metal handbag in grey color* — are juxtaposed with three negative captions c^{neg} (indicated by \times). The open-vocabulary detector is applied to I two times, once for each distinct vocabulary.

light" as an example, a negative caption may be formulated as "a glass lamp emitting blue light".

Formally, with the introduction of object-specific vocabularies, each ground truth object is redefined as $\mathbf{o}_i = (\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_i, \mathcal{V}_i)$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^4$ denotes the bounding box of the object, and $\mathcal{V}_i = \{c_i^{\text{pos}}, c_{i,1}^{\text{neg}}, \dots, c_{i,N}^{\text{neg}}\}$ represents the object-specific vocabulary, which includes the sole positive caption together with all the negative ones. Notice that in this new scenario, \mathcal{V}_i is no longer filled with prompts derived from categorical labels as in classical OVD, but with detailed textual descriptions of objects, which completes the transformation of classical labels into pure natural language.

During inference, the detector is tasked with selecting the most appropriate label for each detected object from its corresponding vocabulary \mathcal{V}_i . For a detection to be considered correct, the predicted label must match the positive caption c_i^{pos} associated with the ground truth object. This approach, which requires the comparison between the positive caption and carefully crafted negatives for each object, challenges open-vocabulary detectors to distinguish the correct object from closely related and semantically distinct alternatives.

We report an example of our ground truth arrangement in Figure 2.

Metrics

To evaluate the predictions, we rely on two complementary metrics: the COCO mean Average Precision (mAP) and the Median Rank. Together, they provide a robust evaluation of both object localization accuracy and the ability to assign the correct caption across varying levels of detection confidence.

The mAP metric offers a detailed performance analysis by measuring how well the detector aligns its predictions with ground truth annotations, considering both spatial overlap and correct label assignment. It focuses on the highest-confidence prediction for each object, providing a comprehensive overview of the detection quality.

In addition to mAP, we also employ the Median Rank metric to assess the detector’s confidence in ranking the correct caption among all possible choices in the vocabulary for each object. Specifically, let $\mathbf{d} = (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{s})$ represent a positive prediction — i.e., which has an Intersection over Union (IoU) of at least 0.5 with a ground truth object \mathbf{o}_i ². To compute the Median Rank, we sort the confidence scores \mathbf{s} in descending order. We then determine the rank of the score associated with the correct caption within \mathcal{V}_i . The final metric is the median of these ranks, aggregated across all objects in the evaluation dataset.

While mAP focuses exclusively on the highest-scoring prediction, the Median Rank provides deeper insights into the detector’s ability to differentiate the correct label from competing options in the vocabulary. Notice that since we are prompting open-vocabulary detectors with natural language instead of standard label-based classes, we had to adjust some inherently class-based post-processing steps for these metrics to work correctly. This is the case for the class-based non-maximum suppression, for which we release more details in [Appendix C](#).

3.2 Dataset

In this work, we introduce both novel test sets equipped with the introduced metrics and

²In cases where multiple predictions meet the IoU criterion for the same ground truth object, the one with the highest confidence score is selected.

proper evaluation protocols (*FG-OVD Benchmarks*) and a weakly-labeled training set (*FG-OVD Train Sets*) designed to enhance fine-grained open-vocabulary detection (FG-OVD). Evaluating open-vocabulary object detectors using the protocol described in Section 3.1 necessitates a dataset specifically designed to handle per-object vocabularies and able to emphasize the quality and diversity of negative examples for each object. This proposed suite comprises eight distinct evaluation scenarios, divided into two primary categories: **Difficulty-based** and **Attribute-based** benchmarks. Difficulty-based benchmarks focus on evaluating the detector’s performance by manipulating the complexity of the negative captions, shifting from easy to very hard negatives. Differently, Attribute-based benchmarks enable targeted assessments by isolating specific attribute types, allowing for a detailed evaluation of a detector’s ability to recognize and distinguish particular object characteristics. In addition to the test sets, we also provide a weakly labeled training dataset.

Instead of reannotating images from scratch, we choose to use PACO ([Ramanathan et al., 2023](#)) as the underlying data source. PACO comes equipped with bounding boxes annotated with a structured description of the underlying object and its attributes. However, these annotations are not immediately suitable for our scenario, as we need a free-form text formulation. To create natural language descriptions of object attributes, we employ a large language model (LLM), transforming structured attribute annotations coming from PACO into rich, descriptive captions. The test sets undergo manual revision to ensure accuracy and high-quality annotations.

The following sections detail the preprocessing of PACO annotations, the transformation of structured attributes into natural language descriptions, and the derivation of positive and negative captions to construct both the benchmark suite and training dataset.

Refining Structured Annotations

In order to obtain detailed natural language descriptions for each object, we first preprocess and clean the structured annotations from the PACO dataset. PACO covers 75 object categories, encompassing 456 object-part categories and 55 attributes across image and video datasets.

Table 1: Statistics of the FG-OVD Benchmarks and Train sets. For each benchmark configuration, we report the number of images (Imgs), the number of annotated objects (Objs), the objects-to-image ratio (Objs/Img), the number of positive captions, the average number of positive captions per image, negative captions per positive caption, and objects per positive caption.

Name	Negative Set Strategy	Imgs	Objs	Obj/Img	✓Caps	✓/Img	✗/✓	Objs/✓
FG-OVD Benchmarks								
Hard	Random attribute subst. (×1)	1707	3545	2.1	2349	1.4	9.9	1.5
Normal	Random attribute subst. (×2)	1537	2968	1.9	2034	1.3	10.0	1.5
Easy	Random attribute subst. (×3)	853	1299	1.5	971	1.1	10.0	1.3
Trivial	Random captions	1707	3545	2.1	2349	1.4	9.9	1.5
Color	Color attribute subst.	1599	3119	2.0	2126	1.3	10.0	1.5
Material	Material attribute subst.	1577	3193	2.0	2128	1.3	10.0	1.5
Pattern	Pattern attribute subst.	321	467	1.5	337	1.0	7.4	1.4
Transparency	Transparency attribute subst.	230	409	1.8	238	1.0	2.2	1.7
FG-OVD Train Sets								
Traning set	Random attribute subst. (×1)	15366	18041	1.2	18041	1.2	10.0	1.0
Validation set	Random attribute subst. (×1)	757	908	1.2	908	1.2	10.0	1.0

Fig. 3: Samples from FG-OVD Benchmarks. Each benchmark tests different properties by crafting negative captions via attribute substitution. Substituted attributes are underlined in the captions.

To improve caption clarity, we remove generic attributes such as *plain* pattern and *opaque* transparency — common across most objects — to prevent unnatural descriptions (e.g., *A plain opaque black dog*). However, these attributes are

retained to generate negative captions. Redundant attributes from object parts are also eliminated to streamline descriptions, with missing details merged into the main object’s attributes. For instance, complex descriptions like *A car with a*

Table 2: Different attribute types and their possible values.

Type	Possible Values		
Colors	black	light blue	blue
	dark blue	light brown	brown
	dark brown	light green	green
	dark green	light grey	grey
	dark grey	light orange	orange
	dark orange	light pink	pink
	dark pink	light purple	purple
	dark purple	light red	red
	dark red	white	light yellow
	yellow	dark yellow	
Materials	text	stone	wood
	rattan	fabric	crochet
	wool	leather	velvet
	metal	paper	plastic
	glass	ceramic	
Patterns	plain	striped	dotted
	checkered	woven	studded
	perforated	floral	logo
Transp.	opaque	translucent	transparent

black hood, black roof, black fender, and black bumper are simplified to *A black car*. Also, parts without attributes are discarded. Since the PACO dataset provides attributes for only some objects and lacks scene-level attribute consistency, there is the risk of generating captions that unintentionally describe multiple objects, leading to incorrect evaluations. To mitigate this, captions are initially propagated to all objects of the same class, and any mismatches are manually revised to ensure consistency and accuracy.

For the attribute-based tests, we primarily adopt attribute values from the PACO dataset, encompassing four types: *29 colors*, *14 materials*, *8 patterns*, and *3 transparency modes*, as better detailed in Table 2. These attributes provide a rich and varied testing ground to evaluate detectors across a wide range of visual properties.

Positive Caption Generation

To generate precise textual descriptions of objects, we assume that each object is characterized by at least one attribute and may contain multiple parts, each with its own attributes. Since open-vocabulary object detectors require textual inputs, we leverage this structured definition to create fine-grained descriptions that incorporate both object-level and part-level details.

To achieve this, we employ a Large Language Model (LLM), specifically OpenAssistant-LLAMA-30B (Köpf et al., 2023), guided by prompt engineering and in-context learning Brown et al. (2020). Specifically, the model is presented with structured object descriptions extracted from PACO along with carefully crafted natural language examples to establish a consistent captioning style (see Figure 4). The LLM then generates new captions based on structured queries describing the attributes and relationships of unseen objects.

To ensure high-quality captions, we implement an *iterative prompting* mechanism to refine outputs when they fail to meet predefined criteria, such as omitting key attributes or exceeding length constraints. If a generated caption does not satisfy our criteria, we issue a series of targeted follow-up queries (see Listing 1), prompting the LLM to correct specific errors. While this methodology could be applied iteratively until all captions are optimal, we found that a single refinement step was sufficient to achieve high-quality results, eliminating the need for further iterations. Captions that still failed to meet the predefined criteria after the follow-up questions were discarded from the dataset to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Following generation, the captions comprising FG-OVD Benchmarks undergo a manual review to ensure consistency and accuracy, reduce annotation errors, and improve alignment with the structured attributes of the dataset.

Negative Captions Generation

To comprehensively evaluate open-vocabulary object detection models, we propose a diverse set of benchmarks incorporating vocabularies with challenging negative captions derived from the generated positive captions. Our goal is to create negatives that are semantically distinct while maintaining structural consistency with their corresponding positive captions.

To achieve this, we employ attribute substitution, where specific attributes in the original caption are replaced while preserving the overall sentence structure. This approach ensures controlled variations while avoiding the syntactic inconsistencies or hallucinations that could arise from modifying the structured object descriptions and re-querying the LLM.

Fig. 4: Caption Generation and Correction. We query the LLM with a JSON description outlining the object’s parts and attributes and provide four in-context samples to mitigate hallucination risks. A *warm-up question* separates the query from the in-context examples and prevents confusing the attributes of the examples with those of the query object. If the initial caption does not meet predefined criteria, we ask follow-up questions (outlined in Listing 1) to address identified issues.

The negative captions are designed to test the model’s ability to handle variations in both **attribute types and quantities**, providing a robust assessment of its resilience to fine-grained distinctions. Our benchmarks are categorized into two main types:

(i) **Difficulty-based benchmarks** (Trivial, Easy, Medium, Hard). These benchmarks assess the ability of detectors to handle progressively more challenging negative captions. In the Trivial setting, negative captions are randomly selected from other objects, while in Easy, Medium, and Hard, negative captions are generated by replacing 3, 2, and 1 attributes, respectively. As fewer attributes are changed, the distinction between captions becomes subtler, making the task increasingly difficult (see Figure 3, top row).

(ii) **Attribute-based benchmarks** (Color, Material, Transparency, Pattern). These benchmarks focus on a detector’s ability to distinguish specific attributes. Negative captions are generated by modifying only one attribute per caption, depending on the benchmark category, allowing for a targeted evaluation of the model’s sensitivity to each attribute type (see Figure 3, bottom row).

The benchmark statistics are detailed in Table 1, providing insights into the distribution and complexity of the generated datasets.

FG-OVD Train Sets

Following the same procedure for the positive caption generation, we generated synthetic training and validation datasets from the PACO-LVIS training and validation sets, respectively. Differently from the FG-OVD Benchmark generation procedure, we did not perform a manual check on these sets due to the high number of samples and the more relaxed quality guarantees. However, to avoid injecting annotation errors, we applied a more conservative policy: the attributes assigned to one object are not propagated to another with unknown attributes in the same image. Therefore, for these data splits we restricted caption generation to instances with a single object of a specific category. This precaution prevents captions intended for one object from inadvertently describing another that lacks ground truth annotations, therefore limiting the presence of wrongly annotated samples.

We opted for generating datasets that adhere to the Hard standard, thus including negative captions that vary from the positive ones by a single attribute only. Additionally, we limited our selection to objects that enabled us to generate 10 negative captions. These parameters were chosen to train models under the most challenging

Listing 1: List of prompts employed in Iterative Prompting for correcting inaccurate captions. Each prompt is accompanied by a comment elucidating the condition that prompts the activation of that particular question.

```

1 followup_prompts = {
2   # caption with more than 60 words
3   0: "Your answer was too long. Create only one sentence for the object that
4     describes what the object looks like considering its attributes",
5   # ' is a ' inside the caption
6   1: "Your answer is a definition of what the object is. Give me a caption
7     that only describes the object and its attributes",
8   # object not inserted
9   2: "You did not specify that you are describing a {object_name}. Reformulate
10    the caption with this addition",
11  # part not inserted
12  3: "You did not specify that the {object_name} has a {part_name}. Reformulate
13    the caption with this addition",
14  # attribute not considered
15  4: "Could you specify that the {attribute.type} of the {object_name} is {
16    attribute.value}?",
17  # ':' in the caption
18  5: "Do not list the elements of the object. Summarize the description of the
19    object in a natural language caption",
20  # more than 2 '''
21  6: "You gave me more than one caption. Summarize them in only one caption",
22  # a number in the caption
23  7: "Your answer contains a number not present in the JSON. Create a new
24    caption considering only the attributes I gave you and without adding
25    information",
26  # only one ''' in the caption
27  8: "Answer is not complete. Write a complete caption",
28  # found an illegal character
29  9: "Illegal characters in the caption. Remove them",
30  # 'or' in the caption
31  10: "Ensure that the attributes are described using 'and' instead of 'or' to
32     correctly represent all the specified attributes.",
33  # 'single' in the caption
34  11: "You used the word 'single'; reformulate the caption without it"
35 }

```

conditions, significantly enhancing their ability to detect subtle distinctions between similar captions.

Table 1 reports statistics of the training and the validation sets.

3.3 The NoctOWL Model

In addition to evaluating state-of-the-art existing models, we introduce NoctOWL to investigate the performance of an in-domain model specifically tailored for fine-grained open-vocabulary detection. NoctOWL is an open-vocabulary object

detection model designed to capture both fine-grained and coarse-grained object details, maintaining strong generalization across diverse types of benchmarks.

Based on the OWL family of open-vocabulary object detectors Minderer et al. (2022, 2023), NoctOWL builds on the assumption that the primary challenges in fine-grained open-vocabulary detection lie in the classification stage rather than in the localization Bianchi et al. (2024). Therefore, we adapt only a small portion of the model, in particular the classification head, while keeping the

rest of the network frozen. The training process is designed to achieve two key objectives:

- Enhancing fine-grained discrimination to improve performance in attribute-level recognition.
- Preserving coarse-grained knowledge to maintain robust detection capabilities in class-level categories and mitigate catastrophic forgetting.

To achieve these goals, we define two complementary loss components: a fine-grained hinge-based triplet loss and a coarse-grained distillation loss, which are combined to form the overall training objective.

Fine-Grained Loss

The fine-grained loss focuses on improving the model’s capability to distinguish subtle details in object descriptions. For each object, represented by a visual feature and associated with a vocabulary containing one positive caption and multiple negative captions, we use a hinge-based triplet loss. The goal is to pull the representation of the correct caption closer to the visual representation of the object while pushing the representations of the incorrect captions further away.

Formally, the fine-grained loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{FG}} = \sum_{i=1}^B \sum_{j=1}^N [\alpha + S(\mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{t}_{i,j}^{\text{neg}}) - S(\mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{t}_i^{\text{pos}})]_+, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v}_i is the visual representation of the i -th object, $\mathbf{t}_i^{\text{pos}}$ is the encoding of the positive caption, $\mathbf{t}_{i,j}^{\text{neg}}$ is the representation of the j -th negative caption, S is the cosine similarity, α is the margin parameter, $[x]_+ \equiv \max(x, 0)$, and B is the batch size.

Coarse-grained Distillation Loss

Training only with the objective expressed in Equation 1 repurposes features to better represent fine-grained attributes but causes catastrophic forgetting of coarse-grained class-level knowledge in the model. To mitigate this, we employ a distillation strategy Li and Hoiem (2017) aiming to retain the model’s ability to recognize coarse-grained object information by preserving the original model’s predictions on a standard class-level vocabulary C . For each training sample, we compute similarity scores between the

visual representation of each object and the entries in the class-level vocabulary using the original model. During training, we encourage the updated model to retain these similarity scores by applying a mean squared error (MSE) loss, ensuring that coarse-grained knowledge is not lost. Formally, the coarse-grained distillation loss is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CG}} = \sum_{i=1}^B \sum_{k \in C} (S(\mathbf{v}_i^*, \mathbf{t}_k) - S(\mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{t}_k))^2, \quad (2)$$

where C is the set of class-level categories, S represents cosine similarity, \mathbf{v}_i^* is the visual representation of the i -th object from the original (pre-trained) model, \mathbf{v}_i is the updated visual representation from the fine-tuned model during training, and \mathbf{t}_k is the text representation of the k -th category in the vocabulary.

The overall training objective is the sum of the fine-grained loss and the coarse-grained distillation loss

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{FG}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{CG}}. \quad (3)$$

This combined loss ensures that the model excels in fine-grained discrimination while preserving its coarse-grained detection capabilities.

4 Experiments

We evaluated the performance of several state-of-the-art open-vocabulary detection models on our *FG-OVD Benchmarks*, following the unified evaluation protocol described in subsection 3.1. In addition to assessing pre-trained models, we trained and analyzed NoctOWL, as detailed in subsection 3.3, investigating how the coarse-grained loss term balances performance between the fine-grained domain and the object-level domain.

4.1 Training Implementation Details

We trained NoctOWL on our *FG-OVD Train Set* using the OWL-ViT (Minderer et al., 2022) and OWLv2 (Minderer et al., 2023) models. Specifically, we introduce two model variants: NoctOWL, initialized from the pre-trained weights of OWL-ViT, and NoctOWLv2, initialized from the pre-trained weights of OWLv2. Both models were trained with ViT B/16 and L/14 backbones.

We trained the models for 20 epochs using a batch size of 32, a learning rate of 3×10^{-5} ,

and a weight decay of 0.1. We perform optimization using the Adam optimizer. During training, we used a triplet loss with a margin of 0.15 and included ten hard negatives for each sample to enhance discriminative learning.

For the coarse-grained loss term, we used the LVIS class set as the reference vocabulary, appended with the prompt "a photo of ", to preserve object-level knowledge during training.

4.2 Evaluated Models

In addition to NoctOWL, we evaluated the performance of ViLD (Gu et al., 2022), Detic (Zhou et al., 2022), CORA (Wu et al., 2023), OWL (Minderer et al., 2022), OWLv2 (Minderer et al., 2023), and GroundingDino (Liu et al., 2023).

Due to the OWL family of models (including NoctOWL) having a positional encoding layer trained with a token limit of 16, we restricted our evaluation to captions that comply with this constraint, covering approximately 80% of the available captions. To ensure fairness, we evaluated all detectors under the same token limit and found no significant impact on results, as detailed in Appendix A.

GroundingDino, originally designed for referring expression comprehension (REC), differs from other detectors as it does not natively support full caption vocabularies as input. To adapt it for open-vocabulary detection, we processed each caption from the vocabulary \mathcal{V}_i separately through a forward pass and merged the predictions for evaluation. Further details on this adaptation can be found in Appendix B.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Performance vs Negative Difficulty

Table 3 presents the mean Average Precision (mAP) of state-of-the-art detectors on our difficulty-based benchmarks, alongside reference results from existing benchmarks for standard open-vocabulary detection. For our evaluations, the dynamic vocabularies were configured with five negative captions ($N = 5$). Overall, all detectors perform well in recognizing and localizing objects described by detailed captions when no confounding labels are present (Trivial setting).

Table 3: Results (mAP) on Difficulty-based benchmarks ($N = 5$) and on LVIS rare categories. Values for LVIS rare are taken from the original papers or GitHub repos.

Detector	LVIS	FG-OVD			
	Rare	Triv.	Easy	Med.	Hard
OWL (B/16)	20.6	53.9	38.4	39.8	26.2
OWL (L/14)	31.2	65.1	44.0	39.3	26.5
OWLv2 (B/16)	29.6	52.9	40.0	38.5	25.3
OWLv2 (L/14)	34.9	63.2	42.8	41.2	25.4
Detic	39.9	69.7	18.6	18.6	11.5
ViLD	16.8	56.6	39.9	36.1	22.1
GDino	18.1	62.7	30.1	27.9	16.6
CORA	22.2	35.1	20.4	20.0	13.8
NoctOWL(B/16)	11.6	46.6	44.4	45.6	40.0
NoctOWL(L/14)	26.0	57.4	54.2	54.8	48.6
NoctOWLv2 (B/16)	17.5	48.3	49.1	47.1	42.1
NoctOWLv2 (L/14)	27.2	57.5	55.5	57.2	50.2

Table 4: Results (mAP) on Attribute-based FG-OVD Benchmarks with two negative captions ($N = 2$).

	Color	Material	Pattern	Transp.
OWL (B/16)	45.3	37.3	26.6	34.1
OWL (L/14)	43.8	44.9	36.0	29.2
OWLv2 (B/16)	45.1	33.5	19.2	28.5
OWLv2 (L/14)	53.3	36.9	23.3	12.2
Detic	21.5	38.8	30.1	24.6
ViLD	43.2	34.9	24.5	30.1
GDino	41.0	30.2	31.2	25.4
CORA	25.0	19.3	22.0	27.9
NoctOWL (B/16)	44.7	46.0	46.1	53.6
NoctOWL (L/14)	53.1	56.9	49.8	57.2
NoctOWLv2 (B/16)	46.8	48.2	42.2	50.2
NoctOWLv2 (L/14)	55.6	57.0	49.2	55.9

However, their discriminative abilities degrade significantly under challenging hard-negative conditions. For instance, while Detic achieves the highest performance in the Trivial setting, it becomes the weakest model when tested in the Hard setting.

Generally, the best mAP in Hard is obtained by methods like OWL and ViLD that carefully embed image-language contrastively learned features into the detector heads. If properly managed inside the architecture, this information is crucial in giving the object detection heads discriminative abilities. Instead, Detic bases its strength on training with large image-level datasets, which add strong class-wise discriminative skills while largely

Fig. 5: Effect of the number of negative captions N . For each one of the eight proposed FG-OVD Benchmarks, we report the mAP (rows 1-2) and the Rank (rows 3-4) varying the number N of negative captions for the different probed detectors. Notice that for Pattern and Transparency, we have a limited number of possible negatives (7 and 2, respectively).

sacrificing fine-grained attribute recognition abilities. This conclusion also seems motivated by the almost zero gain that OWLv2 — trained in a self-supervised manner on web-scale data (10B images) — has with respect to OWL. The training approach of OWLv2 possibly adds visual robustness to the already known classes but fails to inject proper discriminative attribute information despite the massive amount of data employed.

Our baseline method, NoctOWL, which adapts OWL and OWLv2 models, significantly improves performance across every benchmark except Trivial. Every OWL configuration benefits remarkably, achieving substantial performance improvements. For instance, the most powerful model, OWLv2 Large, sees its mAP on the Hard benchmark move from 25.4 to 50.2. This dramatic enhancement demonstrates that FG-OVD training significantly

strengthens the models’ fine-grained discrimination capabilities by introducing a sufficient margin of separation between the correct caption and the challenging hard-negative ones. However, this improvement comes at a slight cost: the performance on the Trivial benchmark and the LVIS benchmark shows a marginal decline. This outcome suggests that learning fine-grained information inherently degrades the model’s ability to handle coarse-grained concepts, but the distillation loss term delivers an improved trade-off and mitigates this issue (see [subsection 4.3.4](#)).

Two qualitative examples in the first row of [Figure 6](#) show how the scores entropy from the different detectors drastically increases when captions in the vocabulary start to contain very hard negatives.

Fig. 6: Output scores from the probed detectors. We report examples of how detectors score vocabulary entries for a specific object. The first green caption is positive, while the other red ones are the negatives. **First row: Hard vs Trivial** – we show the difference in score distributions when detectors are challenged with Hard (left) or Trivial (right). **Second row: Attributes** – we show the behavior when changing specific attributes, like color (left) or material (right). **Third row: Varying the number of negatives** – we show how increasing the number of negatives (left: $N = 2$, right: $N = 5$) strongly challenges the fine-grained discriminative abilities of many detectors.

4.3.2 Performance vs Attribute Type

In Table 4, we present the mAP performance of each evaluated detector in discerning specific attribute types by introducing hard negatives where only a single attribute is altered. To ensure comparability across different attributes, we simplified the task by limiting the dynamic vocabularies to $N = 2$ hard-negative captions³.

As observed, color emerges as the easiest attribute for most detectors, with OWLv2 achieving the best baseline mAP in this category. This trend is likely because color is one of the most commonly represented attributes in web-scale image-text datasets, such as alt-text pairs, used to train contrastive image-language models like CLIP and to generate N-gram vocabulary entries during OWLv2’s self-supervised training stage. Conversely, attributes like transparency and pattern are likely underrepresented in these datasets, which may explain their lower detection performance, even for recent open-vocabulary models such as CORA.

³Different attributes imply varying numbers of potential negatives, but our benchmark always guarantees $N = 2$.

With the introduction of FG-OVD training, the NoctOWL models achieve the best mAPs across all Attribute-based benchmarks. Since the training was conducted in the Hard setting, every attribute type was represented in the training set, enabling the models to develop robust discriminative abilities across a diverse range of attributes. The most significant improvements are observed in the Pattern and Transparency benchmarks, where performance had been relatively poor prior to training. Furthermore, the training also enhances results in the Material benchmark, where distinguishing subtle material differences can sometimes be particularly challenging, even for humans.

The two qualitative examples presented in the second row of Figure 6 illustrate how various detectors respond differently to distinct attribute types.

4.3.3 Performance vs Vocabulary Size

Figure 5 illustrates the mAP and median rank trends as the number of negative captions N in the vocabulary is incrementally increased up to 10 for each benchmark in the evaluation suite. For Pattern and Transparency, the maximum value

of N corresponds to the total number of possible attribute variations.

As expected, an increase in N leads to a decline in detector performance, albeit at varying rates depending on the model. Detic exhibits the sharpest performance drop-off, with both mAP and rank metrics deteriorating rapidly as the number of negatives grows. Conversely, OWLv2 and ViLD demonstrate greater resilience on the Hard benchmark for attributes such as Color and Material, although their performance still lags for Pattern and Transparency. This discrepancy is likely attributable to the limited representation of these attributes in the datasets used during their training and pre-training phases. CORA, on the other hand, struggles to maintain robust performance even when only a small number of negatives are introduced, underscoring the significant challenges faced by contemporary open-vocabulary detectors in distinguishing fine-grained attributes.

NoctOWL demonstrates exceptional robustness to an increasing number of negatives. Although its initial mAP with zero negatives is marginally lower than that of the OWL models, NoctOWL exhibits a steady, linear decline in mAP as the number of negatives (N) increases. This contrasts sharply with the exponential performance degradation observed in most other models, establishing NoctOWL as the top-performing model when faced with a high number of negatives. Notably, as the number of negatives increases, the score distributions for many models exhibit higher entropy, resulting in more frequent misclassifications, as evidenced by qualitative examples in the third row of Figure 6.

4.3.4 Effect of Coarse-grained Distillation

Figure 7 illustrates the effect of the coarse-grained distillation loss term on both FG-OVD and LVIS rare validation sets across training epochs, comparing models trained with and without it.

At the start of training, fine-grained performance improves significantly, as shown by the sharp increase in FG-OVD mAP. However, this rapid enhancement in fine-grained capabilities comes at the cost of severe forgetting of coarse-grained concepts, evidenced by a steep decline in LVIS rare class mAP.

When the coarse-grained loss is applied, LVIS mAP benefits considerably, retaining much of the coarse-grained knowledge even after multiple training epochs. Meanwhile, FG-OVD mAP experiences only a negligible downgrade, demonstrating that distillation effectively mitigates catastrophic forgetting of coarse-grained concepts without substantially compromising fine-grained learning.

These findings underline the trade-off between fine-grained and coarse-grained learning, emphasizing the importance of techniques like distillation to preserve a model’s generalization across diverse benchmarks.

4.4 Additional Results

mAP Small, Medium and Large

Table 5 provides a detailed breakdown of mAP scores across Difficulty-based and Attribute-based benchmarks, categorized by object size. As expected, detection performance declines for smaller objects, as fine details become harder to discern, whereas larger objects allow for more precise attribute recognition.

While NoctOWL follows this general trend, it demonstrates greater robustness to object dimensions compared to other models.

Role of Caption Lengths

Our generated captions exhibit considerable variability in length, influenced by the specific benchmark used. This raises the possibility that the results reported in the paper may be correlated with sentence length. To analyze this effect, we present in Figure 8 the mAP scores evaluated on subsets where captions are grouped by their average word count within the annotation vocabulary.

The results indicate that, on average, task difficulty increases slightly with longer captions, as more detailed descriptions introduce additional complexity. Interestingly, OWL-based detectors and GroundingDINO show a moderate decline in performance as caption length increases, while ViLD, Detic, and CORA demonstrate greater resilience to such variations. However, the overall correlation remains weak, suggesting that caption length does not consistently impact the final results across models.

Fig. 7: Effect of Coarse-grained Distillation loss term during training. X- and Y-axis report mAP on FG-OVD and LVIS-Rare, representing respectively, fine- and coarse-grained performance (upper-right is better). Lines represent the evolution of performance during training **with** and **without** the coarse-grained loss term. The **blue** dot indicates the initial performance before training.

Table 5: Results (mAP) segmented by object sizes (S=Small, M=Medium, and L=Large) on the FG-OVD Benchmarks. Difficulty-based sets (Trivial, Easy, Medium, and Hard) use $N = 5$ negative captions, while Attribute-based ones (Color, Material, Transparency, and Pattern sets) use $N = 2$.

	Difficulty-based ($N = 5$)												Attribute-based ($N = 2$)											
	Trivial			Easy			Medium			Hard			Color			Material			Pattern			Transparency		
	S	M	L	S	M	L	S	M	L	S	M	L	S	M	L	S	M	L	S	M	L	S	M	L
OWL (B/16)	15.0	44.6	60.1	11.6	29.4	44.3	12.5	33.0	43.1	11.0	21.7	28.3	15.6	39.1	48.2	11.2	29.7	42.5	2.7	24.8	28.3	17.0	31.3	37.5
OWL (L/14)	33.0	56.0	67.9	19.3	39.3	42.9	18.3	34.4	39.9	13.8	22.7	27.0	24.1	37.1	45.7	22.0	39.0	47.0	11.2	34.6	35.4	20.1	26.2	30.7
OWLv2 (B/16)	26.3	48.0	54.6	15.9	33.4	44.0	19.5	34.2	38.8	14.8	21.9	26.4	24.5	42.1	44.6	14.9	27.1	37.9	18.0	19.8	20.5	20.2	26.6	29.7
OWLv2 (L/14)	32.0	55.8	65.8	13.8	34.3	48.6	24.2	34.6	43.9	14.0	21.9	26.2	32.2	47.1	53.9	17.1	30.9	40.6	11.2	24.4	22.8	3.9	8.5	15.8
Detic	39.4	71.1	75.0	19.9	19.3	19.1	11.6	20.2	18.4	10.5	11.5	12.2	16.1	23.2	21.1	20.1	39.4	42.2	27.6	33.5	30.5	0.0	28.9	40.0
ViLD	32.5	63.2	61.8	20.8	43.0	44.8	21.6	40.0	38.5	15.0	24.0	23.2	26.3	49.6	44.7	16.7	37.6	39.9	13.0	28.9	24.0	13.9	30.9	34.0
GDino	19.1	58.5	72.4	7.7	30.4	31.9	6.6	28.2	29.8	5.1	17.0	17.0	12.1	39.4	45.9	7.0	28.0	34.4	7.6	26.9	34.7	19.7	22.8	27.6
CORA	12.0	32.9	46.4	6.0	18.5	26.5	7.6	19.1	25.7	4.2	13.2	17.3	9.4	24.8	32.5	7.7	17.0	26.8	4.2	21.9	28.2	10.8	25.8	34.9
NoctOWL (B/16)	16.3	36.8	49.8	15.9	42.7	55.6	13.8	39.2	57.7	14.6	42.5	57.8	17.7	41.2	55.9	15.9	42.9	56.5	21.5	47.7	62.6	11.5	42.6	53.2
NoctOWL (L/14)	25.7	46.8	56.2	28.7	53.1	63.2	30.6	51.5	63.5	30.5	55.0	66.6	29.9	50.6	61.9	29.6	54.8	65.9	35.7	54.9	60.9	17.9	46.7	55.0
NoctOWLv2 (B/16)	24.4	41.9	48.0	24.5	46.4	54.6	23.4	47.2	59.2	24.6	47.9	55.1	27.0	46.5	53.9	24.6	48.2	55.0	30.7	48.2	57.3	19.8	40.2	46.6
NoctOWLv2 (L/14)	28.8	49.8	56.8	30.1	55.8	66.2	24.5	53.9	66.2	29.4	56.0	66.3	29.3	54.1	64.5	30.9	55.9	65.3	22.3	51.4	63.6	11.7	46.6	53.4

Choice of Fine-Grained Loss Function

We compare the impact of training NoctOWL with a cross-entropy (CE) loss versus the hinge-based triplet (Tri) loss. As shown in Table 6, the triplet loss generally demonstrates slightly better mAP on FG-OVD benchmarks, suggesting its enhanced capability in capturing fine-grained distinctions.

On the LVIS benchmarks, the triplet loss outperforms the CE loss across all configurations,

demonstrating its strength in preserving coarse-grained semantic information. These results confirm that triplet loss is a better choice for balancing fine-grained accuracy with coarse-grained generalization.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced a comprehensive evaluation protocol and benchmark suite for Fine-Grained Open Vocabulary Detection (FG-OVD), assessing the fine-grained discriminative power of open-vocabulary detectors. Our protocol challenges models with rich, attribute-based captions

Fig. 8: Effect of the caption length: We illustrate the mAP of detectors across Difficulty-based ($N = 5$) and Attribute-based ($N = 2$) benchmarks, with varying caption lengths for objects. Captions are categorized into four groups based on their average word count inside the corresponding vocabulary: *short* (6 or fewer words), *medium* (7-10 words), *long* (11-14 words), and *longer* (15 or more words). OWL-based detectors are excluded from the *longer* group due to their inability to process captions exceeding 16 tokens.

Table 6: Effect of the choice of the fine-grained loss term \mathcal{L}_{CG} on LVIS rare and Difficulty-based ($N = 5$) and Attribute-based ($N = 2$) FG-OVD Benchmarks.

		FG-OVD Benchmarks									
		LVIS		Difficulty-based				Attribute-based			
Detector	Loss	Rare	Triv.	Easy	Med.	Hard	Color	Material	Pattern	Transp.	
OWL	B/16	CE	10.4	49.8	44.3	45.3	44.2	44.2	45.3	44.3	49.8
OWL	B/16	Tri	11.6	53.6	46.1	46.0	44.7	44.7	46.0	46.1	53.6
OWL	L/14	CE	24.9	56.6	51.3	56.4	52.0	52.0	56.4	51.3	56.6
OWL	L/14	Tri	26.0	57.2	49.8	56.9	53.1	53.1	56.9	49.8	57.2
OWLv2	B/16	CE	14.9	48.3	42.8	47.0	45.8	45.8	47.0	42.8	48.3
OWLv2	B/16	Tri	17.5	50.2	42.2	48.2	46.8	46.8	48.2	42.2	50.2
OWLv2	L/14	CE	25.3	54.5	50.2	55.1	54.0	54.0	55.1	50.2	54.5
OWLv2	L/14	Tri	27.2	55.9	49.2	57.0	55.6	55.6	57.0	49.2	55.9

and provides meaningful metrics to evaluate their performance.

To create these benchmarks, we leveraged structured object descriptions and used an LLM to generate diverse, high-quality captions. By systematically modifying attributes, we established a range of difficulty levels, enabling a thorough analysis of model weaknesses.

Our experiments revealed a significant gap in detectors’ ability to capture fine-grained object properties, with even the latest models struggling

in complex scenarios. We also introduce a weakly-labeled FG-OVD training set and release NoctOWL, an OWL-based model specifically devised for FG-OVD. Our results demonstrate that adapting detectors on the fine-grained domain significantly improves detection performance, particularly in hard-negative settings, while distillation techniques help mitigate catastrophic forgetting of coarse-grained concepts.

In the future, we aim to develop improved pre-training strategies for vision-language backbones in open-vocabulary object detection models. We

envision more balanced image-text representations that seamlessly integrate both fine- and coarse-grained features without relying on a specially curated dataset tailored to a fixed set of attribute types.

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Appendix A Model Architectural Details

In our experiments, we evaluated the following architectural configurations for each detector:

- **OWL-based models (OWL-ViT and OWLv2)**: We tested configurations using ViT B/16 and ViT L/14 as backbones.
- **ViLD**: The model was configured with a ResNet-152 backbone and a distillation weight of 0.1.
- **Detic**: We used the Swin-B backbone with ImageNet-21K pretraining, specifically the Detic_LC0C0I21k_CLIP_SwinB_896b32_4x_ft4x_max-size configuration.
- **GroundingDINO**: The GroundingDINO-T variant was used, featuring a Swin-T backbone.
- **CORA**: The model was evaluated with a ResNet-50x4 backbone.

Since the captions in our benchmarks are written in natural language, all models were tested without any additional pre-appended prompts. The only exception was CORA, which inherently utilizes an internal prompt ensemble of 80 different prompts. To assess the impact of this ensemble, we also evaluated CORA with the prompt ensemble disabled, processing input captions without modifications. As shown in Figure A1, the results indicate that performance remains largely unchanged, suggesting that the prompt ensemble does not significantly affect the model’s overall effectiveness.

OWL Subset

Since OWL-based detectors can only process sentences with a maximum length of 16 words, we re-evaluated all detectors on a filtered version of the benchmarks, where captions exceeding this limit were removed. The updated benchmark statistics reflecting this constraint are provided in Table A1.

The corresponding results for all models on this subset are reported in Table A2, Table A3, and Figure A2. Notably, the removal of longer captions had a minimal impact on overall performance, with each detector maintaining the same general trends observed in the full benchmark. This suggests that key information is typically conveyed early in the captions, making the omitted portion of longer sentences largely redundant.

Appendix B Handling Grounding Dino

GroundingDino differs from other detectors in its design, as it is primarily intended for referring expression comprehension (REC) and does not support full caption vocabularies as input. Unlike other models, which process an entire set of captions at once, GroundingDino requires a single caption per inference. While its authors suggest that certain prompts can automatically segment textual expressions (e.g., using the ”.” character), we observed inconsistencies: single-word labels are handled correctly, but complex sentences are sometimes split incorrectly.

To adapt GroundingDino for open-vocabulary detection, we perform inference for each caption in the vocabulary individually. Each prediction is represented as $d_i = (\mathbf{b}_i, h_i, t_i)$, where \mathbf{b}_i refers to the bounding box coordinates, h_i represents the score assigned to the caption t_i , and t_i is the caption itself. This approach differs from other open-vocabulary object detectors, where each prediction includes a score array \mathbf{s}_i , with each element reflecting the score for its corresponding caption. However, this distinction does not influence the mAP of the detector, as it only takes into account the predicted label for each bounding box. On the other hand, this difference does affect the rank metric, since the score array \mathbf{s}_i for the vocabulary entries is required for ranking.

Fig. A1: Effect of the number of the prompt ensemble on CORA

Table A1: Benchmark based on OWL-compatible captions: Statistics of the benchmarks based on OWL-subset benchmark for each different negative set comprising the number of images (Imgs), the number of annotated objects (Objs), objects-to-image ratio (Objs/Img), positive captions, positive captions per image, negative captions per positive caption, and objects per positive caption.

Name	Negative Set Strategy	Imgs	Objs	Obj/Img	✓Caps	✓/Img	✗/✓	Objs/✓
Hard	Random attribute subst. ($\times 1$)	1390	2903	2.1	1816	1.3	9.9	1.6
Normal	Random attribute subst. ($\times 2$)	1187	2293	1.9	1483	1.2	10.0	1.5
Easy	Random attribute subst. ($\times 3$)	417	657	1.6	445	1.1	10.0	1.5
Trivial	Random captions	1389	2888	2.1	1810	1.3	10.0	1.6
Color	Color attribute subst.	1269	2485	2.0	1595	1.3	10.0	1.6
Material	Material attribute subst.	1277	2611	2.0	1639	1.3	10.0	1.6
Transparency	Transparency attribute subst.	177	323	1.8	180	1.0	2.0	1.8
Pattern	Pattern attribute subst.	188	294	1.6	193	1.0	7.2	1.5

For rank computation, where we rank all possible vocabulary items for each object, we considered all predictions d_j generated for the ground truth object o_i , without applying the typical class-agnostic NMS used in our evaluation. Instead, we nullified the confidence scores of predictions that did not overlap with the ground truth, i.e., $h_j \leftarrow 0$ if $IoU(o_i, d_j) < 0.5$. The ranking score s_i is determined by selecting, for each vocabulary element of o_i , the prediction score corresponding to the caption with the highest confidence. The median rank is then calculated using the same procedure applied to the other detectors.

Appendix C Post-processing Adjustments

Since we now rely exclusively on natural language descriptions instead of fixed categorical labels and

we are dealing with a per-object vocabulary, some standard inference-time operations used in classical object detection require careful reconsideration. The most critical post-processing operation is class-aware non-maximum suppression (NMS), which is traditionally employed to remove redundant predictions of the same class at the same location while allowing predictions from different classes to coexist.

However, in our scenario where all vocabulary entries are mutually exclusive, and there is no longer a valid notion of *overlap* among labels, class-aware NMS would basically perform no filtering at all. This has an important effect on COCO mAP, which does not penalize predictions from incorrect classes. In our scenario, this means that if an incorrect prediction with higher confidence overlaps with the correct one, it does not result in any penalty. In other words, even a single

Table A2: Benchmark based on OWL-compatible captions: mAP on Difficulty-based benchmarks ($N = 5$).

	Backbone	Trivial	Easy	Med.	Hard
OWL	B/16	53.9	38.4	39.8	26.2
OWL	L/14	65.1	44.0	39.3	26.5
OWLv2	B/16	52.9	40.0	38.5	25.3
OWLv2	L/14	63.2	42.8	41.2	25.4
NoctOWL	B/16	46.6	44.4	45.6	40.0
NoctOWL	L/14	57.4	54.2	54.8	48.6
NoctOWLv2	B/16	48.3	49.1	47.1	42.1
NoctOWLv2	L/14	57.5	55.5	57.2	50.2
Detic		68.1	22.3	20.9	12.3
		(-1.6)	(+3.7)	(+2.3)	(+0.8)
ViLD		54.8	44.0	38.2	22.8
		(-1.8)	(+4.1)	(+2.1)	(+0.7)
GDino		62.6	35.1	32.0	18.7
		(-0.1)	(+5.0)	(+4.1)	(+2.1)
CORA		33.3	23.2	21.8	13.4
		(-1.8)	(+2.8)	(+1.8)	(-0.4)

low-confidence correct prediction, from the mAP perspective, *masks* all the more significant errors.

To avoid this problem, we instead employ the *class-agnostic* NMS procedure. In this way, a higher-confidence incorrect prediction will suppress a lower-confidence correct one, regardless of the class label, avoiding the masking problem arising in the class-aware NMS. This adjustment forces metrics like mAP to reflect errors appropriately, aligning the evaluation process with the requirements of our framework.

Appendix D Additional Benchmark Samples

We show additional samples from our benchmarks in Figures D3 (Color), D4 (Material), D5 (Pattern), D6 (Transparency), D7 (Trivial), D8 (Easy), D9 (Medium), and D10 (Hard).

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Table A3: Benchmark based on OWL-compatible captions: mAP on Attribute-based benchmarks ($N = 2$).

	Backbone	Color	Mat.	Pat.	Transp.
OWL	B/16	45.3	37.3	26.6	34.1
OWL	L/14	43.8	44.9	36.0	29.2
OWLv2	B/16	45.1	33.5	19.2	28.5
OWLv2	L/14	53.3	36.9	23.3	12.2
NoctOWL	B/16	44.7	46.0	46.1	53.6
NoctOWL	L/14	53.1	56.9	49.8	57.2
NoctOWLv2	B/16	46.8	48.2	42.2	50.2
NoctOWLv2	L/14	55.6	57.0	49.2	55.9
Detic		23.2	38.8	31.1	21.8
		(+1.7)		(+1.0)	(-2.8)
ViLD		43.9	34.7	25.6	27.6
		(+0.7)	(-0.2)	(+1.1)	(-2.5)
GDino		43.2	30.9	31.1	26.9
		(+2.2)	(+0.7)	(-0.1)	(+1.5)
CORA		24.3	17.3	16.9	28.4
		(-0.7)	(-2.0)	(-5.1)	(+0.5)

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A black plastic helmet
 A dark purple plastic helmet
 A light red plastic helmet

A black ceramic mug
 A dark orange ceramic mug
 A green ceramic mug

A black ceramic bowl
 A light orange ceramic bowl
 A grey ceramic bowl

A light brown paper bag
 An orange paper bag
 A light purple paper bag

Fig. D3: More samples from the Color benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

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A white towel made of fabric
 A white towel made of paper
 A white towel made of crochet

A white ceramic plate
 A white fabric plate
 A white paper plate

A light brown paper bag
 A light brown fabric bag
 A light brown velvet bag

A white ceramic bowl
 A white glass bowl
 A white plastic bowl

Fig. D4: More samples from the Material benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

A brown wool hat with a woven pattern
 A brown wool hat with a dotted pattern
 A brown wool hat with a plain pattern

A grey floral patterned pillow made of fabric
 A grey woven patterned pillow made of fabric
 A grey studded patterned pillow made of fabric

A dark blue ceramic vase with an orange and light blue floral pattern
 A dark blue ceramic vase with an orange and light blue checkered pattern
 A dark blue ceramic vase with an orange and light blue perforated pattern

A blue plastic studded rimmed bowl
 A blue plastic striped rimmed bowl
 A blue plastic dotted rimmed bowl

Fig. D5: More samples from the Pattern benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

A transparent glass lamp with a light yellow bulb
 A translucent glass lamp with a light yellow bulb
 A opaque glass lamp with a light yellow bulb

A transparent glass vase
 A opaque glass vase
 A translucent glass vase

A orange plastic glass with a translucent body
 A orange plastic glass with a opaque body
 A orange plastic glass with a transparent body

A light grey plastic transparent soap dispenser
 A light grey plastic opaque soap dispenser
 A light grey plastic translucent soap dispenser

Fig. D6: More samples from the Transparency benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

Fig. D7: More samples from the Trivial benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

- A light yellow plastic cup with a text pattern
- A black velvet cup with a perforated pattern
- A blue crochet cup with a checkered pattern
- A dark pink fabric cup with a checkered pattern
- A dark brown leather cup with a dotted pattern
- A light pink velvet cup with a woven pattern

- A wood table with a brown top and grey metal legs
- A wood table with a green top and dark brown wool legs
- A crochet table with a brown top and light blue plastic legs
- A velvet table with a brown top and purple plastic legs
- A ceramic table with a brown top and blue crochet legs
- A wood table with a blue top and dark red paper legs

- A black remote control with grey buttons and a plastic back
- A dark yellow remote control with dark purple buttons and a glass back
- A light brown remote control with dark blue buttons and a velvet back
- A yellow remote control with light blue buttons and a wood back
- A orange remote control with light green buttons and a text back
- A dark red remote control with light brown buttons and a wool back

- A perforated bench with a brown wooden seat
- A studded bench with a red crochet seat
- A floral bench with a light pink plastic seat
- A dotted bench with a light red stone seat
- A plain bench with a dark yellow fabric seat
- A checkered bench with a light orange stone seat

Fig. D8: More samples from the Easy benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

A book with a light grey cover made of paper
 A book with a dark pink cover made of rattan
 A book with a dark green cover made of glass
 A book with a dark green cover made of metal
 A book with a light red cover made of metal
 A book with a dark red cover made of glass

A light grey metal bench
 A red wood bench
 A dark purple velvet bench
 A dark red rattan bench
 A black wood bench
 A purple fabric bench

A knife with a grey metal blade
 A knife with a light green wool blade
 A knife with a dark pink velvet blade
 A knife with a dark purple paper blade
 A knife with a dark orange wool blade
 A knife with a light red plastic blade

A mirror with a brown wooden frame
 A mirror with a orange rattan frame
 A mirror with a light grey fabric frame
 A mirror with a blue leather frame
 A mirror with a black metal frame
 A mirror with a light yellow glass frame

Fig. D9: More samples from the Medium benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),

A light grey bicycle with metal handlebars and black wheels
 A light grey bicycle with wood handlebars and black wheels
 A light grey bicycle with leather handlebars and black wheels
 A light orange bicycle with metal handlebars and black wheels
 A light grey bicycle with stone handlebars and black wheels
 A dark yellow bicycle with metal handlebars and black wheels

A remote control with a white plastic back
 A remote control with a white paper back
 A remote control with a light purple plastic back
 A remote control with a dark blue plastic back
 A remote control with a white rattan back
 A remote control with a white leather back

A grey trash can made of plastic
 A grey trash can made of paper
 A red trash can made of plastic
 A dark purple trash can made of plastic
 A grey trash can made of fabric
 A grey trash can made of leather

A black laptop with a blue glass screen
 A black laptop with a blue wool screen
 A black laptop with a blue text screen
 A light pink laptop with a blue glass screen
 A black laptop with a blue fabric screen
 A black laptop with a blue metal screen

Fig. D10: More samples from the Hard benchmark. Legend: OWL (L/14), OWLv2 (L/14), Detic, ViLD, GDino, Cora, NoctOWL (L/14), NoctOWLv2 (L/14),